

INCREASING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN THE ART OF MUSIC

Makhmudov Jakhongir Saminjon ugli

Student of Namangan State University

E-mail: Jahongirmahmudov1997@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article deals with increasing the interest of students of general secondary schools in the art of music and wide promotion of the art of music.

Key words: music, art, musical instruments, musical instrument, ethics, aesthetics, emotion, culture, melody.

Music actively affects the child's soul, plays an important role in the formation of his moral and aesthetic image. Therefore, the main goal of music education is to educate students in musical culture, which is a component of human spiritual culture. To achieve these goals, the music teacher has the following tasks: increase students' interest in the art of music; development of musical-artistic taste and the need for musical activities; content of the range of knowledge and skills about music; development of feelings of artistic creativity in the course of musical activities; moral and aesthetic upbringing of children through the artistic and ideological content of the works; in the process of music lessons, instilling enthusiasm for profession and work.

The level of professionalism of the music teacher is of great importance in the implementation of these tasks. First of all, a music teacher should be a highly cultured, creative, inquisitive, scientific worldview person who loves his profession and children from the bottom of his heart. It is necessary to give a good lesson in accordance with modern science and technology requirements and use every minute of it productively. Only a teacher who has learned to work on himself, who can choose from among them what is necessary for his subject in the era of modern science and technology development and increased information, can develop the ability to know students, think independently, and work independently.[1]

In order to be a good teacher, a music teacher should know pedagogy and psychology, children's physiology, theory of aesthetics and ethics, literature and music teaching methodology. Because these determine the children's character, what they are inclined to, what methods can be used in the teaching process.

A music teacher should have sufficient knowledge, skills and experience in the theoretical and practical fields of music. That is, he should work as a musician, singer,

choir conductor, accompanist, music theorist and writer. As a creative music teacher, he is also the author of the script for the one-hour lesson, its artist-performer and director, therefore, the music lesson is an art lesson.

The criterion of the teacher's skill is determined by the mastery and discipline of the students. If he constantly works on himself, observes and learns the experiences of advanced teachers in the field of education and training, and applies it to his work, he can improve his pedagogical skills. A skilled teacher will always have a high reputation among students, because he can find the right way to the hearts of students.[2]

A special feature of the teaching profession is to love and care for children. If a teacher does not know children's desires and inner world and is not interested in them, he cannot be a teacher, because children like kind, humble, cheerful, sincere, self-respecting and demanding teachers. The morals of the teacher should be pure, religious, pious and exemplary in all aspects. His appearance, in general, should be orderly, neat, and he should be an example with his cultural and modest dress. Every word of his can be seen positively by the students. A music teacher shows his characteristic features. This reveals the individual style of the teacher's activity, that is, the unique combination of methods and ways that ensure the best performance of his work.

The first and primary component of a music teacher's ability is talent. He embodied in himself the sum of anatomical and physiological signs, the characteristics of the type of higher activity. Talent can bring out the ability in this sense, but it cannot determine it in advance. Talent does not appear ready-made before development and separate from it, it is not the first sign and invariable characteristic of an individual, it is formed in the process of educating an individual. Ability is one of the prerequisites for successful work in the field of teaching.[3]

The music teacher must have professionally acquired general pedagogical skills:

- students' knowledge and education in music
able to determine the level;
- ability to plan the development of students and class children;
- which students may encounter in learning music
able to anticipate difficulties and possible mistakes;
- based on musical educational methods, tools and organizational forms
ability to choose;
- taking into account the level of education and upbringing of the educational material to be able to select, analyze and synthesize;

The idea that the teacher is the main person in the school is even more evident when it is applied to the music teacher. The child is not the main object of upbringing or education. He is a thinking and active breed. A teacher should be as eager as a

scientist to perceive the ways in which his personality can reach perfection. In fact, it is less.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that the methodology of teaching music in general secondary schools, increasing the interest of young people in the art of music, and widely promoting the art of Uzbek music are the most important tasks for every music pedagogue. one of the big tasks.

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